

First Stage: Task Assessment

I consider the **interaction between data scientists and software engineers to be relevant** for this activity:

	Agree	Partially Agree	Partially Disagree	Disagree
Data Access Definition				
Data Selection				
ML Model Evaluation				
ML Artifact Storage				
ML Model Availability				
ML Model Integration				
ML Model Deployment				

Second Stage: Recommendation Assessment

1-) Involve data scientists and business owners when eliciting and analyzing requirements

I consider this recommendation **relevant to the interaction between data scientists and software engineers** during this activity:

	Agree	Partially Agree	Partially Disagree	Disagree
Data Access Definition				
Data Selection				
ML Model Evaluation				
ML Artifact Storage				
ML Model Availability				
ML Model Integration				
ML Model Deployment				

2-) Provide ML literacy for all project stakeholders

I consider this recommendation **relevant to the interaction between data scientists and software engineers** during this activity:

	Agree	Partially Agree	Partially Disagree	Disagree
Data Access Definition				
Data Selection				
ML Model Evaluation				
ML Artifact Storage				
ML Model Availability				
ML Model Integration				
ML Model Deployment				

3-) Develop documentation for product requirements, system architecture, and APIs at collaboration points

I consider this recommendation **relevant to the interaction between data scientists and software engineers** during this activity:

	Agree	Partially Agree	Partially Disagree	Disagree
Data Access Definition				
Data Selection				
ML Model Evaluation				
ML Artifact Storage				
ML Model Availability				
ML Model Integration				
ML Model Deployment				

4-) Define clear responsibilities and internal processes with clear boundaries for data scientists and software engineers

I consider this recommendation **relevant to the interaction between data scientists and software engineers** during this activity:

	Agree	Partially Agree	Partially Disagree	Disagree
Data Access Definition				
Data Selection				
ML Model Evaluation				
ML Artifact Storage				
ML Model Availability				
ML Model Integration				
ML Model Deployment				

5-) Support interdisciplinarity between data scientists and software engineers

I consider this recommendation **relevant to the interaction between data scientists and software engineers** during this activity:

	Agree	Partially Agree	Partially Disagree	Disagree
Data Access Definition				
Data Selection				
ML Model Evaluation				
ML Artifact Storage				
ML Model Availability				
ML Model Integration				
ML Model Deployment				

6-) Organize regular meetings for showcasing team activities

I consider this recommendation **relevant to the interaction between data scientists and software engineers** during this activity:

	Agree	Partially Agree	Partially Disagree	Disagree
Data Access Definition				
Data Selection				
ML Model Evaluation				
ML Artifact Storage				
ML Model Availability				
ML Model Integration				
ML Model Deployment				